

STRUCTURE OF TAPETAL CELLS OF BARLEY (HORDEUM VULGARE L.)

Efendieva Kamala

*PhD in Biology,
Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Baku*

Abstract

Tapetal cells, like other parietal layer cells were small and oblong in the beginning. Shortly afterwards they increased in size and became binucleate, their cytoplasm being densely stained with haematoxylin. Not a few cells of the tapetum showed chromatin granules in their nuclei. At the pollen tetrad stage, the tapetal cells had attained their maximum growth.

The submicroscopic structure of the tapetal cells of the barley anthers has been investigated at the stages of a late tetrad and uninucleate pollen grain before and after vacuolization. The tapetal cells of the barley as regards their structure and functions at these stages of development may be characterized as secretory ones. Their cytoplasm is abundant with cell organelles. Numerous mitochondria and a Golgi apparatus are in close vicinity with the cisterns of an endoplasmic reticulum. The presence of ribosomes on the outer cisternae of the stack relates the entire structure to the endoplasmic reticulum. Osmiophilic substances appear in several places with respect to the tapetal cells. At the stage of an uninucleate pollen grain instead of the degenerated primary walls, surrounding every tapetal cell, a new wall is formed, which consists mainly of sporopollenin.

Keyword: barley, tapetum, ultrastructure, anther, organelles, development.

Introduction

The mature anther wall consists of several layers: epidermis, endothecium, middle layer and tapetum. These layers differ in cell structure and fulfil a specific function [11,12,20]. Tapetal cells of plant anthers are rich in proteins, fats, starch, amino acids, enzymes and hormones [6,10]. The presence of these substances in tapetal cells indicates their high physiological activity, which is characteristic of secretory cells.

Various cell organelles are involved in the formation and transport of secretion products in secretory cells, including tapetal cells of cereals. Examples of localisation of various substances, their secretion and transport in the cisternae of the endoplasmic reticulum are given in the literature. Along with the endoplasmic reticulum, dictyosomes are also the site of secretion synthesis and transport.

The present work presents the results of the study of ultrastructural changes in barley tapetum cells from the time of establishment to their degeneration.

Material and methodology

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) anthers were examined. The material was fixed with 2.5% glutaric aldehyde in phosphate buffer pH-7.2 for 3 hours. Then anthers were additionally fixed in 2% OsO₄ solution. Casting was carried out in epon 812. Sections were prepared using an LKB ultramicrotome and contrasted with lead citrate according to Reynold's method. Sections were examined using a JEM-7 electron microscope.

Research results

The outer wall of each of the four microsporangia of the barley anther consists of epidermis, endothecium, middle layer and tapetum. The tapetum of barley anther consists of a single layer of cells and completely surrounds the sporogenic cells. The ultrastructure of tapetal cells changes during differentiation and secretion.

Tapetal cells at the stage of secondary archesporium formation are connected with each other and with

sporogenic cells by plasmodesmata. The nuclei of tapetal cells on sections are round or oval. The outer nuclear membrane is granular and very often connected to the endoplasmic reticulum /ER/. Tapetal cells at the secondary archesporium stage are rich in cytoplasmic organelles. Mitochondria are numerous. They are heterogeneous in size, both small and large ones are found. In each mitochondrion, usually 3-4 cristae are found. Mitochondria are evenly distributed throughout the cell volume.

Plastids have the highest electron density. The profile of plastids is elongated, oval. Some plastids contain a small starch granule. The ER is strongly developed. Numerous membranes anastomose with each other. The surface of the ER channel is densely and evenly covered with ribosomes. The Golgi apparatus is rare. Dictyosomes consist of 4-5 paired membranes. Few small Golgi vesicles are detached from the edges of the dictyosomal cisternae and are observed at the terminal ends of the dictyosomes and near them in the cytoplasm.

In the course of further anther development, changes in the structure of organoids of tapetal cells occur. During the formation of microsporocytes, the density of cytoplasm matrix increases. The nucleus with a clearly distinguishable nucleus, occupies the central part of the cell. The matrix of mitochondria is electronically dense. The number of cristae has increased, the number of cristae reaches 6-7 per mitochondrial slice. Plastids of tapetal cells can be oval, round, elongated with electron-dense matrix. Some plastids contain a single starch granule. Long ER channels surround the nucleus and sometimes form a concentric membrane-ergastoplasm. In the meiosis phase, the number of Golgi apparatus elements in the cytoplasm of tapetal cells has markedly increased compared to the previous stage. Each dictyosome consists of 4-5 cisternae surrounded by numerous vesicles of different size with granular content. Large vesicles are located throughout the cytoplasm and near dictyosomes, their content is

electron-transparent. Small vesicles with grey content are located only at the terminal ends of dictyosomes.

At the stage of formation of tetrads of microspores, the inner tangential sheath of tapetal cells thickens. The radial wall adjacent to it is also partially thickened. In this phase of anther development, the tapetal cells form proorbiculae-grey bodies located between the tapetal cell sheath and the plasmalemma. Later, sporopollenia are deposited on the proorbiculae and they become orbiculae. The cytoplasm of tapetal cells at the stage of formation of tetrads of microspores differs in ultrastructure from the previous stages. The mitochondria of the tapetum at this stage are rounded or oval in shape and contain 2-4 rather narrow, long or sickle-shaped cristae. Narrow long ER channels are strongly developed at the tetrad stage. The size of the plastids has increased. In earlier phases, up to the tetrad stage, plastids did not contain osmiophilic globules. At this stage they contain starch granules and numerous osmiophilic globules. At the tetrad stage of microspores, tapetal cells are characterised by maximum development of the Golgi apparatus.

As the microspores emerge from the tetrads, the tapetum begins to degenerate. The disorganisation of organelles continues during the development of the uninucleate microspore and is completed at the stage of the two-cell pollen grain. However, the development of a single-nucleated pollen grain is rather long and we have conditionally divided it into three stages.

At the stage of early vacuolisation of microspores, lysis of the inner tangential sheath of tapetal cells, previously somewhat thickened, occurs. Proorbiculae are formed between the tapetal sheath and the plasmalemma. Subsequently, sporopollenin is deposited on the proorbiculae and they become orbiculae. At this stage, the ER is strongly developed. The other organelles do not differ significantly from those at the tetrad stage.

At the stage of late vacuolisation of microspores, when a central vacuole is formed in the pollen grain, the inner tangential and radial sheaths of tapetal cells practically disappear, sometimes only the middle lamina remains. Tapetal cells contain one or two oval-shaped nuclei. Chromatin is not evenly distributed throughout the nucleoplasm. Individual clots of chromatin are adjacent to the nuclear envelope. The nucleus is usually oval in shape, located in the centre of the nucleus or displaced to its periphery.

Thickening of the cytoplasm matrix of tapetal cells indicates the beginning of cell degeneration.

Signs of degeneration are associated with a decrease in the number of ribosomes, disorganisation of ER, cisterns of dictyosomes and destruction of part of mitochondria. The latter at this stage contain strongly swollen cristae resembling rounded bubbles in their shape. By the time of tapetum cell destruction, most plastids lack starch granules, only some plastids carry large starch granules. The long channels of the ER are fragmented and disintegrate into short sections. Its membranes partially lose ribosomes. Dictyosomes consist of 4-5 closely appressed parallel cisternae, with small vesicles near the ends of the cisternae. Sporopollenin continues to accumulate on the surface of each orbicle. The matrix of the cytoplasm of tapetal cells is

now entirely electron-transparent. By the time of formation of a two-celled pollen grain, disintegration of the cytoplasm of tapetum cells is completed. After disintegration of the cytoplasm of tapetal cells, a tapetal film remains in the anthers, which is fully formed by the time of formation of a uninucleate pollen grain with a central vacuole. The tapetal film, which is of sporopollenin nature, covers the entire tapetal cell like the exine of pollen grains.

Our electron microscopic study allows us to describe in detail the ultrastructure of actively secreting tapetum cells during the period when sporopollenin shells with their constituent orbiculae are formed. All sporopollenin sheaths are formed in the tapetal cell during the period of formation of the uninucleate pollen grain. The sporopollenin-secreting cells of barley tapetum are characterised by a strong development of rough ER, high electron density of the hyaloplasm, a large number of dictyosomes, and the appearance of osmiophilic particles and starch grains in the plastids.

Thus, by the time pollen grains mature, tapetum development ceases. The following ultrastructural peculiarities are indicators of degeneration in tapetum cells, preceding complete lysis of cytoplasm: electron-transparent hyaloplasm, decrease in the number of free ribosomes, formation of autolytic vacuoles, shortening of ER channels, merging of plastids and ER, the latter sometimes surrounding them. The exit of osmiophilic bodies beyond the plasmalemma along the radial walls was noted.

In the mature anther, only the sporopollenin sheath (tapetal film) with orbiculae included in its composition remains from the tapetum.

Discussion of results

A number of researchers have established that the tapetum plays an important role in normal pollen development, since all substances entering the sporogenic cells must inevitably pass through the tapetum [8,9,10,17,18,19,22,24]. The ultrastructure of differentiated tapetal cells of barley anthers is generally similar to that of secretory cells of other plants [5] and animals [15]. This similarity is particularly clear in the number and arrangement of the ER, the membranes of which often form an ergastoplasma. Unusual enlargement of endoplasmic reticulum was also found in tapetal cells of other plants: *Sileno* [15], *beta vulgare* [16].

A large number of granular ER is characteristic of protein-producing cells. The development of ER in tapetum cells may be associated with the realisation of a similar function. As is known, the tapetum borders the tissue of microspore mother cells and developing pollen grains. These cells must accumulate substances used in their development. Fragmentation of ER cisternae and vesicle formation during tapetal cell degeneration may be related to the processes of movement of spare substances. ER channels mediate the transport of protein hydrolysis products and are also the site of enzyme synthesis. The disintegration of ER can also lead to the release of hydrolytic enzymes.

The function of the Golgi apparatus is probably also related to the secretory activity of the tapetum [1]. At different stages of anther development, the Golgi apparatus is similar to the ER in the nature of its changes. During differentiation of tapetal cells, the number of

Golgi apparatus components on a slice increases and reaches a maximum at the tetrad stage. Similar data were obtained when studying tapetal cells of other plants [13]. In other plant cells, it was found that the number of dictyosomes, their total size, and the nature and size of vesicles detached by dictyosomes change in the process of cell differentiation depending on tissue specialisation and functional load of organelles [2].

The content of a large number of dictyosomes in tapetal cells indicates that synthetic processes are intensively taking place in barley tapetal cells. In meristematic cells mitochondria have weakly contrasting membranes, cristae are few. As cells differentiate, cristae develop, the contours of the outer and inner membrane with cristae become sharp. The number of cristae tends to increase [3]. As cells age, mitochondrial cristae undergo reduction and destruction [23]. The morphological changes of mitochondria during tissue differentiation are probably related to changes in the physiological state of the cell [4].

During anther development in barley tapetal cells, we found the same change in mitochondria.

We observed a large number of free ribosomes in barley tapetal cells. A detailed picture was observed by Echlin and Godovin [13].

In the mature anther, only the sporopollenin sheath/film/ with its constituent orbiculae remains in the tapetum cells [14,21,25]. It has been established that in cereals, orbiculae serve as a place of attachment of pollen grains [7].

Conclusions

1. Tapetum cells in the developing anther in the process of formation of secondary archesporium, meiocytes and pollen grains from meristematic cells become secreting cells, then their cytoplasm undergoes lysis.

2. Each stage of the developing tapetal cell is characterised by a specific ultrastructure.

3. In the mature anther, only the sporopollenin sheath formed during cell development, with its constituent orbiculae, remains.

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